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EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY FOR WELDING TECHNOLOGY OF THERMOSET FRP

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Back Ground

	Thermoset (TS) CFRP	Thermoplastic (TP) CFRP	Target
Reliability (Mechanical property)	<i>Cross-linked structure</i>	<i>Non cross-linked structure (Low Creep and Fatigue)</i>	<i>Designed cross-linked structure</i>
Thermal Stability	<i>High</i>	<i>Thermal deformation</i>	<i>High</i>
Prepreg cost	<i>Low</i>	<i>High (Impregnation issue)</i>	<i>Low</i>
Molding time	<i>Cure time issue (Generally long)</i>	<i>Heat & Cool Time (Generally short)</i>	<i>Fast-Cure Technology (Resin, Process)</i>
Molding Conditions	<i>Low Temp. & Pressure</i>	<i>High Temp. & Pressure</i>	<i>Low Temp. & Pressure</i>
Assembly / Bond	<i>Not Weldable (Adhesive / Fastener)</i>	<i>Weldable</i>	<u>Weldable</u>

Concept

- ✓ Laminate structure
 - Multiple configuration (UD, Fabric etc.)
- ✓ Utilize superior TS CFRP properties
 - Mechanical, Thermal, Dimensional stability
- ✓ Embedding of TP domain on surface
 - Design TP domain thickness at micro-scale (μm)
 - Various TP can be applied
- ✓ Utilize surface TP domain as welding component
 - Efficient process (Only surface requires heat)
 - Stable process (Inner TS is stable under heat)

FRP Laminate (after curing) with Weldable surface

Actual cross section of CFRP

Welding Technology of Thermoset FRP

Example of Welding Cycle

CFRP

Heat Temp.: Based on TP property

Strong Joint strength

No Interfacial Delamination

Experimental Method

Sample Preparation

I) Sheet fabrication & Lamination

Fixed CF: T700S
(Lab. Trial)

Prepreg: T700S/2592
Lamination: $[0/90]_{ns}$

II) Thermal Welding

Heat Plate Press: 3min, 3MPa

Temperature: 180C, 240C

Ref. Adhesive (Recommended Condition)

Evaluation of Bonding Strength

III) Lap Shear Test: ISO-4587

Tensile speed 2mm/min, CFRP 1mmt

IV) Cross Peel Test: JASO M406-87

Compression speed 5mm/min, CFRP 2.5mmt

Sample List

No	Bonding Method	Bonding Component	Bonding Condition
#1	Welding	Polyamide (PA: Tm215C) 100µm	240C, 3min (No surface treatment)
#2		Polypropylene (PP: Tm160C) 100µm Un-modified PP	180C, 3min (No surface treatment)
#3		Polypropylene (m-PP: Tm160C) 100µm Modified PP	180C, 3min (No surface treatment)
#4	Adhesive (Reference)	Epoxy based (Structural adhesive) Panel bond 8115@3M	Recommended condition 100µm w/ sand blast, 60C, 3hr
#5		Urethane based MG5000/5038@ETEC	Recommended condition 100µm w/ sand blast, RT, 3days

Results

Lap Shear Test

Cross Peel Test

Confirmed equivalent bonding strength to structural adhesive with welded PA, m-PP Thermoplastic

Analysis

Bonding Strength & Fracture surface of Lap Shear sample

#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
PA	PP	m-PP	Epoxy	Urethane
26.3MPa	3.4MPa	24.9MPa	20.2MPa	9.3MPa
Mixture of adherend and cohesive failure	Delamination from CFRP to PP	Cohesive failure at m-PP	Cohesive failure	Cohesive failure

- ✓ For modified-PP, cohesive failure similar to structural adhesive
- ✓ For PA, mixture of adherend and cohesive failure

Modeling of Numerical Simulation

2D FEM Simulation

- ✓ Stress analysis of TS/TP interface by placing three CFs longitudinally from the surface
- ✓ Simulation conducted for tensile & shear, and CF/TP interface strength also examined

TS/TP interface position

Mesh Condition for TS/TP interface (TP0.5)

Numerical Study 1

Tensile Analysis

Simulation for TP0.5

Contact between CF and TP generates high stress,
TS/TP interfacial debond occurs without CF/TP contact

Numerical Study 2

Shear Analysis

Simulation for TP0.5

Numerical Study 3

Influence of CF/TP interfacial strength

Bonding strength is improved with increase in interfacial strength of CF/TP

When the interfacial strength becomes sufficiently high, failure transitions to TP cohesive failure

Conclusion & Future Work

- ✓ Confirmed material concept by embedding a thermoplastic domain in the thermoset CFRP for a bonded structure.
- ✓ Confirmed equivalent bonding strength for thermoplastic embedded thermoset CFRP compared to an adhesively bonded structure.
- ✓ 2D numerical analysis shows the interface between CF and thermoplastic domain is an important parameter that governs the bonding strength.
- ✓ It is suggested that delamination or debond does not occur at the interface between the TS/TP domain, but at the strong interface between CF and thermoplastic domain.

Aim to explore market opportunities for “Welding technology for Thermoset FRP” with further experimental and mechanism validation